

Google data analytics certificate notes

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Course 1:

- Data is a collection of facts that can be used to draw conclusions, make predictions, and assist in decision-making.
- data analysis is the collection, transformation, and organization of data in order to draw conclusions, make predictions and drive informed decision-making.
- Data science may have one of three types:
 - o **Statistics:** The excellence of statistics is rigor. Statisticians are essentially philosophers, epistemologists. They are very, very careful about protecting decision-makers from coming to the wrong conclusion.
 - o **Machine learning:** Performance is the excellence of the machine learning and AI engineer. Where machine learning engineers are the ones who take the challenge to build systems that are very accurate and stay dedicated to do the task.
 - o **Analytics:** The excellence of an analyst is speed. Analysts surf and explore vast amounts of data and find use of it quickly and efficiently.
- **Data ecosystems** are made up of various elements that interact with one another in order to produce, manage, store, organize, analyze, and share data. a data ecosystem used by a human resources department. would include information like postings from job websites, stats on the current labor market, employment rates, and social media data on prospective employees. A data analyst could use this information to help their team recruit new workers and improve employee engagement and retention rates. And there are many other examples of data ecosystems.
- The difference between a data analyst and a data scientist:
 - o Data science is defined as creating new ways of modeling and understanding the unknown by using raw data.
 - o Data scientists create new questions using data, while analysts find answers to existing questions by creating insights from data sources.
- Difference between data analytics and data analysis:
 - o data analysis is the collection, transformation, and organization of data in order to draw conclusions, make predictions, and drive informed decision-making.
 - o Data analytics in the simplest terms is the science of data. It's a very broad concept that encompasses everything from the job of managing and using data to the tools and methods that data workers use each and every day.
- data-driven decision-making process:
 - o **Ask** questions and define the problem.
 - o **Prepare** data by collecting and storing the information.
 - o **Process** data by cleaning and checking the information.
 - o **Analyze** data to find patterns, relationships, and trends.
 - o **Share** data with your audience.
 - o **Act** on the data and use the analysis results.
- EMC Corporation's data analytics life cycle is cyclical with six steps:

- Discovery
- Pre-processing data
- Model planning
- Model building
- Communicate results
- Operationalize
- An iterative life cycle was created by a company called **SAS**, a leading data analytics solutions provider. It can be used to produce repeatable, reliable, and predictive results:
 - Ask
 - Prepare
 - Explore
 - Model
 - Implement
 - Act
 - Evaluate
- A project-based data analytics life cycle has five simple steps:
 - Identifying the problem
 - Designing data requirements
 - Pre-processing data
 - Performing data analysis
 - Visualizing data
- Big data analytics life cycle:
 - Business case evaluation
 - Data identification
 - Data acquisition and filtering
 - Data extraction
 - Data validation and cleaning
 - Data aggregation and representation
 - Data analysis
 - Data visualization
 - Utilization of analysis results
- Analytical skills are qualities and characteristics associated with solving problems using facts. And can summed in the following:
 - curiosity, it is about wanting to learn something.
 - understanding context, it is about understanding the structure of something or the environment and where the information fits in the big picture.
 - having technical mindset, the ability to break things down into smaller pieces.
 - data design, is how you organize information
 - data strategy, management of people processes and tools used in data analysis
- Analytical thinking: it has different parts, such as:
 - visualization,
 - strategy,
 - problem-orientation,
 - correlation,

- big-picture and detail-oriented thinking.
- When thinking analytically of a problem you can start by asking:
 - What is the root cause of a problem? And that can happen by asking “Why” for as many times needed. For example you can find that you cannot make a blueberry pie now because the snow storm a few months ago.
 - What are the gaps in the process? Which means finding what needs to be done now to be where you want to be in the future.
 - What did we not consider before? And that helps in finding what is missing from the process and in finding better ways to move forward.

the data analysis process phases:

- ask,
- prepare,
- process,
- analyze,
- share,
- act

Data life cycle:

- plan,
- capture,
- manage,
- analyze,
- archive
- destroy

data life cycle informed by Harvard University research has eight stages:

1. Generation
2. Collection
3. Processing
4. Storage
5. Management
6. Analysis
7. Visualization
8. Interpretation

Most common tools for data analysts to use every day:

- Spreadsheets
- Query languages for databases
- Visualization tools